

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHER.

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Abstract: In this article, the main areas of development of the professional-methodical competence of the future elementary school teacher are researched from a scientific and theoretical point of view.

Key words: integration, trajectory, complex, teaching method, logical method, situation-illustration, cognitive activity.

By improving the methodical training of the future primary school teacher, the main areas of development of his competence elements are as follows:

1) specially selected methodological task systems (V.G. Gilev [32], N.G. Kilina [102], V.I. Mishin [167], G.I. Sarantsev [210, 211] and others);

2) development of special methodological skills of teaching to work with mathematical tasks (O.I. Chikunova [255] and others); organization of extracurricular activities in mathematics (E.V. Vostokova [27], S.V. Demisenova [60] and others); Designing the learning process of the elementary mathematics course theory course (N.V. Sidorova [215], I.S. Zayats [86] and others); designing a task system (O.N. Orlyanskaya [182] and others); creation of specialized elective/facultative courses (V.A. Dalinger [57] and others); pedagogical research transfer skills (IV. Vladikina [26], G.A. Fedorova [240] and others);

3) integration of methodological cycle courses - "elementary mathematics" and "methodology of teaching mathematics" (O.B.Episheva [68], A.J. Jafyarov [82], V.F. Lyubicheva [129], Z.I. Yansufina [267] and others); "mathematics teaching methodology", "psychology" and "pedagogy" (N.L. Stefanova [225] and others); "mathematics teaching methodology" and "history of the development of mathematics" (T.S. Polyakova [196] and others); 4) Integration of traditional and innovative approaches in primary education - activity-based, integrative, differentiated and technological (S.V. Demisenova [60], L.P. Shebanova [258], Z.I. Yansufina [267] et al.); activity-based and technological (O.B.Episheva [68], G.V.Khoreva [246] and others); classification of school and HEI education based on levels and specialization (I.V. Drobisheva [62], O.B.Episheva [77, 79], E.I.Lyashchenko [131], R.A.Uteeva [239] et al.); [267] et al.); activity-based and technological (O.B.Episheva [68], G.V.Khoreva [246] and others); classification of school and HEI education based on levels and specialization (I.V. Drobisheva [62], O.B.Episheva [77, 79], E.I.Lyashchenko [131], R.A.Uteeva [239] et al.); 5) improvement of pedagogical practice (V.A. Dalinger [50], L.V. Sabanova [204], T.G. Cheshuina [254], R.R. Shakhmarova [257] and others);

6) development of creative methodical activity experience (A.P. Zenkovich [90], G.D. Glazer [33], E.I. Malakhova [135] and others);

7) improving the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching mathematics. humanization of mathematical education (T.A. Ivanova [92], Z.M. Kondrashova [109] and others); activity-

based approach (V.A. Dalinger [51, 52], O.B. Episheva [77] and others); developmental education (V.A. Dalinger [53] and others).

8) designing the professional development trajectory of the future primary school teacher (V.M. Monakhov [171] et al.); 9) development of professional competence of primary school teacher: professional and pedagogical (V.A. Dalinger [56], V.A. Demin [59] and others); technological (O.B. Episheva [71] and others); methodical (N.V. Grizlova I.A. Novik [176], T.B. Rudenko [202] and others); informative/information (V.A. Adolf [4], M.P. Lapchik [121], L.B. Senkevich [213] and others); socio-cultural (S.V. Pakhotina [185] and others); analytical/analytical (I.A. Abramova [3] and others) [144].

As noted by scientist V.A. Slastyo: [219, p. 104], the teaching method performs important functions; with its help, the following is carried out: a) delivery of the content of the studied topics to students, b) management of cognitive activities of students, c) intellectual development of students, g) formation of necessary personal qualities. The concept of "teaching method" has been given various definitions in pedagogical and methodological studies: - these are: the system of pedagogical rules and regulatory principles of teacher and student activity (M.I. Makhmutov [159]); an organized complex set of didactic methods and tools that implement the goals of teaching, upbringing and development (V.A. Oganessian [161]); method of interactive activity of teachers and students (Y.K. Babansky [28]; R.S. Cherkasov, A.A. Stolyar [162] et al.; O.M. Zheleznyakova [175]; V.A. Sitarov [217]).

In the opinion of scientist N.G. Khodireva [245, 11 p.], according to the activity-based concept of designing the educational process in higher education institutions, teaching methods are the methods of teacher activity that organize the student's educational/learning/learning activities, lead to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and personal development understood.

Analysis of these and other studies: a) if the teacher's leading role is assumed in the structure of the teaching/learning process, then the teaching method is defined as a method of organizing students' learning activities and managing these activities; b) if the direction of learning is assumed, then the teaching method is defined as a method that helps students move from ignorance to knowledge under the guidance of the teacher; c) logical-content teaching method is defined as a logical method that helps students to consciously master knowledge, skills and abilities.

Most traditional teaching methods [28, 34, 70, 126, 159, 181, 219, et al.] put the teacher, not the learners, at the center of learning/teaching. For example, the classification of scientists such as E. V. Perovsky, E. Ya. Golanta [34] according to the source of information transmission (verbal/verbal, visual and practical methods) is based on the types of teacher's activities and does not reveal the activities of students and the mental processes associated with them. M.N. Skatkin, I.Ya. Lerner's [126] classification by the type of cognitive activity (explanatory-illustrative/demonstrative, reproductive, problem statement/presentation, heuristic and research methods), although it implies a transition to methods that involve the gradual (gradual) development of low-level independence of students, it does not reveal the methods of mastering the knowledge and skills of students.

Among the traditional teaching methods used in higher education, many researchers (E.P. Belozertsev [186], M.Ya. Vilensky [24], V.A. Slastyonin [219], etc.) distinguish the following: lecture (problematic, binary, visual, lecture-consultation, lecture-press conference, lecture-conversation, lecture-discussion, etc.) seminar (abstracts, reports, messages, "round

discussion"/round table), practical and laboratory training, game teaching methods (business game, analysis of educational and professional situations, "brainstorming"/brainstorming, etc.) and independent work of students (advice/consultation, etc.). The traditional theoretical orientation of education prevails in HEIs. The approach, which is the basis of the competence-building approach, and focuses on the development of students' cognitive activity by selecting the teaching methods from the subject's point of view, is insufficiently used in HEIs, which reduces the level of methodological training of students.

In the 60s and 70s of the 20th century, the issue of the need to further develop students' existing knowledge in improving traditional teaching methods began to be studied. Heuristic and problem-based methods based on didactic (business) games, further improvement of technical educational tools to enrich students' knowledge and organize their independent education.

So, the main difference between traditional and active learning methods is the strengthening of activity-oriented learning process. In our opinion, the most complete classification of active teaching methods is based on the researches of scientist E.P. Belozertsev as follows [186, pp. 276-277]:

1) non-imitation methods; various lectures, "round discussion", colloquium, programmed education, seminar, mobile training with thematic discussion, work with small groups and Olympiad;

2) imitative: a) non-game methods (situational solutions, completion of individual tasks, discussion of developed options, holding a seminar, individual trainer, teacher's summary of training, i.e. completion of the lesson and evaluation of students

b) game methods (multiple choice of the optimal solution, brainstorming, business games, role-playing games, game design of individual technological process).

There are also classifications of active learning methods focused in a narrow sense (areas). For example, O. M. Zheleznyakova [175] considered the most productive methods of problematic, dialogic and personalized statement, heuristic dialogue, research method, analysis of production situations, direct and reverse question-and-answer, aimed at forming the qualities of an expert personality. shows. In our opinion, the method of analyzing production situations implies the use of all other methods listed above, because brainstorming is important in situation research.

Since one of the components in the structure of the concept of "professional-methodical competence" of a future primary school teacher is personal qualities of professional importance (chapter 1, clause 1.1, p. 23-25), we analyze the concept of "educational-methodical situation".

"Situation" from a psychological point of view is a system of external conditions that motivate and mediate the activity of the subject [217]. From the point of view of professional activity, "situation" is a set of facts, events and problems related to the description of a certain period or event in the activity that requires appropriate actions [217].

Some researchers (V.A. Slastyonin [217], D.V. Chernilevsky, O.K. Filatov [252], etc.) use active teaching methods as close as possible to the real professional and pedagogical situations in which the future teacher may find himself. is called the method of creating pedagogical situations. For example, V.A. Slastyonin [219, 189 p.] and V.A. Sitarov [217, 235 p.] define several groups of methods of creating problem learning situations as a special class of pedagogical situations that implement the following types of student initiative:

1) methods that motivate students' cognitive activity, for example, the method of unexpected solutions - it is appropriate to use it when the teacher offers a new, previously unused solution to a certain problem that contradicts the existing experience of students, that is, when giving students tasks with an unknown end. This forces students to ask questions that focus on obtaining additional information;

2) methods encouraging independent demonstration of initiative: training in methods of independent creative composition of tasks, searching for analogues similar to events in everyday life;

3) methods using the initiatives put forward during the activity; method of deliberate, deliberate errors: in this, students will have to find and correct the error made by the teacher during the activity.

In the method of joint search for solutions, the teacher deliberately chooses the wrong way to achieve the goal, and the students are required to identify it, offer alternative methods and ways of solving the task. "Labyrinth" method: students are offered 5-6 ready-made solutions on the topic and they have to find the optimal solution. Method of solving practical problems: in this the teacher creates a situation of social importance and students have to prepare themselves for the upcoming activity;

3) Methods of organizing initiative in collective and cooperative activities: the teacher creates situations that ensure competition in the game, study, work and other types of student activities, as well as their initiative in educational and extracurricular activities.

Scientists such as D.V. Chernilevsky and O.K. Filatov [252] distinguish four types of situations according to their educational, educational function:

1) situation-problem (students find the cause of the described situation, pose a problem and solve it);

2) evaluation-situation (students evaluate the decisions made);

3) situation-illustration (students get examples of the main topics of the course based on the issues and problems that need to be solved);

4) case-exercise (students practice verbally solving problems and examples using the analogy/analogy method).

So, all these studies serve as a certain theoretical basis for the development of a holistic concept for the development of professional-methodical competence of the future primary school teacher in the practice of teaching at the pedagogic higher education institution. However, for this, it is necessary to determine the methods and means of its development.

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